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FACTORS INFLUENCING VIETNAMESE STUDENT'S CHOICE ON DESTINATION FOR STUDYING ABROAD: A CASE STUDY OF RUSSIA

Abstract. The objective of this study is to analyze the influence of factors on the choice of Vietnamese students for study abroad in Russia. Research data were collected from 210 Vietnamese students currently studying in Russia through a convenient sampling method. The study used descriptive statistics and exploratory factor analysis (EFA) to answer the research questions. Research results show that 31 criteria are classified into 5 groups of factors affecting the choice of Vietnamese students to study in Russia, including (1) personal improvement, (2) images of educational institutions, (3) destination image, (4) promotional information about higher education in Russia, and (5) cost issues. Based on the results of the study, the article has proposed some important recommendations to motivate Vietnamese students to study in Russia as well as students from many different countries around the world.

Keywords: educational destination, educational tourism, choice of a destination for study abroad, higher education in Russia, study abroad, Vietnamese students, international education

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ФАКТОРЫ, ВЛИЯЮЩИЕ НА ВЫБОР ВЬЕТНАМСКИМИ СТУДЕНТАМИ НАПРАВЛЕНИЯ ДЛЯ ОБУЧЕНИЯ ЗА РУБЕЖОМ (НА ПРИМЕРЕ РОССИИ)

Целью исследования является анализ влияния факторов на выбор вьетнамских студентов для обучения в России. Исследование основано на опросе 210 вьетнамских студентов, обучающихся в настоящее время в России, с помощью метода репрезентативной выборки. Методы исследования - описательная статистика и исследовательский факторный анализ (EFA). В результате изучения был выделен 31 критерий, характеризующий факторы, влияющие на выбор вьетнамских студентов России как учебной дестинации. Все критерии сгруппированы по 5 группам факторов, влияющих на выбор вьетнамских студентов для обучения в России, в том числе (1) личное совершенствование, (2) имидж учебного заведения, (3) имидж дестинации, (4) рекламная информация о высшем образовании в России и (5) вопросы стоимости. По результатам исследования в статье предложен ряд важных рекомендаций для мотивации вьетнамских студентов, а также студентов из разных стран мира получать образование в России.

Ключевые слова: образовательная дестинация, образовательный туризм, мотивация студентов в выборе образовательной дестинации, высшее образование в России, обучение за рубежом, вьетнамские студенты, международное образование

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1. Introduction

The Russian education system is considered one of the best in the world. According to open data from the Ministry of Science and Higher Education of the Russian Federation, Russia currently has more than 700 universities and the number of students in the country is about 4 million people. The Russian Federation is one of the leading countries in terms of accepting students from abroad. In recent years, there has been an increase in the number of international students studying in Russia. The total number of foreign students receiving higher education in Russia has increased over the past three years by more than 26,000 people. Specifically, in 2019, nearly 298,000 international students were studying at higher education institutions in Russia; By 2020 this number has grown to approximately 315,000 international students, and in 2021, the number of international students has increased to about 324,000 students [16].

The relevance of the issues of attracting international students and developing higher education for Russia is of particular importance in the context of establishing friendly relations, including with Southeast Asian countries. In particular, Vietnam is one of the Southeast Asian countries that has a close relationship with Russia. Since 1955, the Democratic Republic of Vietnam and the Soviet Union have officially signed the first agreement on cooperation in education and training. Therefore, the number of Vietnamese students studying in Russia is increasing. Every year, Russia also provides many scholarship packages for cooperation agreements between Russia and Vietnam for Vietnamese students. This is also one of the factors that help Vietnamese students come to study in Russia. However, it is not the main reason for Vietnamese students to choose to study in Russia. This scholarship category is not only available in Russia but also in many other countries around the world. Therefore, the purpose of this paper is to study the factors affecting the choice of Vietnamese students to study abroad in Russia.

2. Research methods and models

2.1. Research methods

This paper used qualitative research methods including research methods and document synthesis. We have synthesized and analyzed scientific articles related to destination choice, and factors affecting students' choice of study abroad destination. The collection of previous studies to have a solid theoretical basis for building research hypotheses and models. The expert interview method was also used in the article to determine the model, scale, and survey variables.

Besides, we also combined with quantitative research methods and built a questionnaire. According to Hair et al. [4], the minimum expected sample for performing exploratory factor analysis (EFA) needs to be 5 times the total number of observed variables. Therefore, the minimum sample size of this study was 160, corresponding to the 32 variables identified. To ensure the sample size condition, we conducted a survey for 210 Vietnamese students currently studying in Russia. The survey was conducted using a Google form. The questionnaire used the Likert scale (5 levels) to measure students' attitudes toward choosing a destination to study abroad through the following groups of factors: personal improvement, the image of educational institutions, destination image, promotional information, and cost issues. Collected information was processed by SPSS software and analyzed data: Descriptive statistics technique, Cronbach's Alpha analysis, exploratory factor analysis (EFA), and regression analysis.

2.2. Research models

Most of the previous studies only analyzed the process and factors affecting students' decision to choose a study destination but did not have a specific research model. Therefore, the author has continued to research and inherit from related studies, and formed a research model of factors affecting students' decisions in choosing a study abroad destination including five factors:

- 1) personal improvement [1–3, 6, 9, 12, 13, 15];
- 2) images of educational institutions [1, 2, 6, 7, 9–12, 14, 15];
- 3) destination image;

- 4) promotion information [6, 7, 9–14];
- 5) cost issues [1–3, 6–11, 13, 14].

The proposed research model is summarized in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 – Proposed model to evaluate factors affecting students' decision to choose a destination to study abroad

Hypotheses in the research model:

- **Hypothesis H1:** Personal improvement has a positive effect on students' decision to choose a study abroad destination.
- **Hypothesis H2:** The image of educational institutions has a positive effect on students' decision to choose a study abroad destination.
- **Hypothesis H3:** Destination image has a positive effect on students' decision to choose a study abroad destination.
- **Hypothesis H4:** Promotional information has a positive effect on students' decision to choose a study abroad destination.
- **Hypothesis H5:** Cost issues have a positive effect on students' decision to choose a study abroad destination.

3. Results

3.1. General information about the survey sample

The survey results in Table 1 indicate that there were more females (68.6%) than males (31.4%) among the 210 students who were surveyed. Of these, between 18–25 years of age (82.9%), between 26–35 years of age (14.3%), and above 35 years of age (2.9%). This study focuses on surveying Vietnamese students currently

studying in Russia. Therefore, a question was included in the questionnaire to confirm this issue. The results show that 100% of the students surveyed are currently studying in Russia. Regarding the level of education that Vietnamese students are currently studying in Russia, 74.3% of bachelor's students, master's students (20%), and PhD students account for 5.7%.

Table 1 – An overview of the survey participants

		Number of participants (n)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	66	31.4
	Female	144	68.6
Age	18–25	174	82.9
	26–35	30	14.3
	Above 35	6	2.9
The survey students are currently studying in Russia	Yes	210	100.0
	No	0	0
The level of education that Vietnamese students are studying in Russia	Bachelor's student	156	74.3
	Master's student	42	20.0
	PhD student	12	5.7

3.2. Analysis of factors affecting the choice of Vietnamese students to study abroad in Russia by EFA

We first tested the quality of the scale using Cronbach's Alpha coefficient. This coefficient was used to ensure the reliability of the scale and observed variables. The requirement for the scale to be accepted is that the variables have a total correlation coefficient greater than or equal to 0.3 and Cronbach's Alpha coefficient greater than or equal to 0.6. (Hair et al., 2006). Variables that do not meet the requirements will be removed from the scale. Based on the proposed research model, we have built a survey questionnaire and conducted a survey for Vietnamese students studying in Russia. In the model, we built the dependent variable and 5 independent variables with a total of 32 observations. According to the results of the quality inspection of the scale, the factors are guaranteed

to be tested, because both the Item-Total correlation coefficient and the Cronbach's Alpha coefficient were satisfactory (Table 2).

The results from Table 2 show that the lowest Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of the scales was 0.725 and the corrected item-total correlation

coefficient of the smallest representative variable was 0.342. The corrected item-total correlation coefficients of the observed variables in the scale were all greater than 0.3. Therefore, all 32 observed variables were accepted and they will be used in exploratory factor analysis.

Table 2 – Test results of Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of the scales

Items	Total number of variables	Corrected Item-Total Correlation (choose the smallest representative)	Cronbach's Alpha Total
PI (Personal improvement)	5	0.565	0.858
II (Image of educational institutions)	7	0.455	0.896
DI (Destination image)	4	0.542	0.809
PR (Promotional information)	6	0.570	0.848
CI (Cost issues)	5	0.544	0.814
DC (Decide to choose a study abroad destination)	5	0.342	0.725

Table 3 – Synthetic results of the rotation matrix table of factors used in the research model after removing the inappropriate variable Rotated Component Matrix^a

Factor name	Variable name	Component				
		1	2	3	4	5
Images of educational institutions in Russia (7 variables)	II7. Have links with educational institutions in Vietnam known to me	.827				
	II2. Reputation and expertise of Lecturers	.764				
	II6. Recognized by employers	.694				
	II4. Large campus and excellent facilities	.669				
	II1. Reputation for education quality	.624				
	II3. Abroad range of courses and programs	.543				
	II5. Have a large number of Vietnamese students enrolled	.519				
Promotional information about higher education in Russia (6 variables)	PR3. Programs promoted through the internet		.843			
	PR2. From recommendations of relatives, friends, colleagues etc.		.778			
	PR1. Information from professionals		.741			
	PR4. Reference from information on social networks		.739			
	PR6. Information from word of mouth		.672			
Personal improvement (4 variables)	PR5. Promotional information from newspapers, magazines, etc.		.664			
	PI3. Want to experience new/different places			.872		
	PI4. Want to experience different cultures and ways of life			.841		
	PI2. Want to improve language skills			.699		
Destination Image (4 variables)	PI1. Want to improve and increase my knowledge			.665		
	DI3. Friendly local people				.844	
	DI1. Russia has beautiful and attractive scenery and natural resources				.694	
	DI4. Safe destination and stable social security situation				.662	
Cost issues (5 variables)	DI2. Accommodation facilities and restaurants of good quality				.648	
	CI3. Job opportunities					.794
	CI5. Low racial discrimination					.794
	CI4. Safe environment (low crime)					.702
	CI2. Low cost of living					.642
	CI1. Low tuition fees					.543
Coefficient KMO		0.604				
Extracted variance (%)		68.854				
Sig. in Bartlett's Test		0.000				

Some important criteria in exploratory factor analysis include: $0.5 < KMO$ (Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin) < 1 [5], Factor loading must be greater than 0.5 and Total variance extracted must be greater than 60%. After conducting exploratory factor analysis for the first time for dependent variables, the results obtained 26 variables were satisfactory and distributed into 5 groups. An observed variable with KMO coefficient was empty, so it was removed from the scale. After that, the study performed the second exploratory factor analysis with the remaining 26 variables (Table 3).

According to the analysis results, from 26 observed variables, the Varimax rotation analysis method gave 5 factors with KMO coefficient of 0.604 (> 0.5), so the factor analysis is suitable for the survey data. Barlett's test has $Sig.<0.05$, this shows that the observed variables were linearly correlated with the representative factor. The extracted variance value was 68.854%. This demonstrates that 68.85% of the variation of the data was explained by the 5 factors generated. Besides, all variables have a load factor greater than 0.5 and ensure differentiation, so the EFA method has practical meaning.

According to the results of the correlation analysis, we continue to perform Multiple Regressions Analysis including five independent

variables in Multiple Regression Analysis (Table 4) to test the influence of factors on Vietnamese students' choice to study in Russia. The analysis results in Table 4 show that $Sig = 0.000 (< 0.05)$, so the regression model was consistent with the collected data and the variables were statistically significant at the 0.05 level. The value of $F=93,969$ was used to test hypothesis H_0 , which shows a significant linear relationship with $p < 0.05$. Hypothesis $H_0: \beta_1 = \beta_2 = \beta_3 = \beta_4 = \beta_5 = 0$.

The adjusted R^2 coefficient of the regression model was 69%. This shows that the independent variables included in the regression analysis were influenced by 69% of the change of the dependent variable in deciding the choice of Vietnamese students to study in Russia. The remaining 31% was the influence of other factors outside the model and random error. The coefficient of variance exaggeration VIF of the independent variables included in the model were all less than 2, so it can be concluded that there was no multicollinearity phenomenon. Thus, the independent variables were not correlated with each other. The results of the regression coefficient test show that the independent variables had a significance level (Sig.) less than 0.05, so they had a correlation with the dependent variable with a confidence level of over 95%.

Table 4 – Results of regression analysis of factors affecting the decision of Vietnamese students to choose to study abroad in Russia

Model	Adjusted R Square	F	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics
			B	Std. Error	Beta		VIF
(Constant)	.690	93.969	-.428	.203		.036	
Personal improvement			.233	.040	.275	.000	1.472
Images of educational institutions			.229	.039	.292	.000	1.665
Destination Image			.220	.037	.271	.000	1.390
Promotional Information			.224	.032	.280	.000	1.065
Cost Issues			.214	.036	.276	.000	1.426

As shown in Table 4, all five variables were the statistically significant level less than 0.05; This proves that we had enough statistical evidence to reject hypothesis H_0 . Therefore, it can be concluded that all 5 independent variables had an impact on Vietnamese students' decision to

choose to study in Russia. These factors were significant in the model and they had a positive impact on the choice of Vietnamese students because the regression coefficients were positive. From the results of the regression analysis, we set up a standardized regression equation as follows:

$$DC = 0.292*II + 0.280*PR + 0.276*CI + 0.275*PI + 0.271*DI$$

The model indicated that the independent variables positively influenced 95.0% of Vietnamese students' choice of study abroad destination. Through the data shown in the regression equation, under the condition that the remaining independent variables remain unchanged and when evaluating the variable "images of educational institutions" (II) increased by one unit, lead to a change of the variable "decision to choose a study abroad destination" increased by 0.292 units; if promotional information (PR) increased by one unit, the decision to choose a study abroad destination went up by 0.28 units; if the variable of "cost issues" (CI) increased by one unit, the change of the variable "decision to choose a study abroad destination" raised by 0.276 units; if the variable of "personal improvement" (PI) increased by one unit, the decision to choose a study abroad destination increased by 0.275 units, and if the destination image (DI) increased by one unit, the change of the variable "decision to choose a study abroad destination" grew by 0.271 units.

Table 5 – Summary of hypotheses and results

<i>Hypothesis</i>	<i>Decision</i>
H₁: Personal improvement has a positive effect on students' decision to choose a study abroad destination (+)	Accepted
H₂: The image of educational institutions has a positive effect on students' decision to choose a study abroad destination (+)	Accepted
H₃: Destination image has a positive effect on students' decision to choose a study abroad destination (+)	Accepted
H₄: Promotional information has a positive effect on students' decision to choose a study abroad destination (+)	Accepted
H₅: Cost issues have a positive effect on students' decision to choose a study abroad destination (+)	Accepted

Through the standardized Beta coefficients, we can know the importance of the factors affecting the choice of Vietnamese students to study abroad in Russia. In particular, "the image of

educational institutions in Russia" was the most influence (0.292), followed by "promotional information" (0.28), "cost issues" (0.276), "personal improvement" (0.275), and the factor "destination image" was the least influence (0.271) on the choice decision of Vietnamese students.

The data in Table 5 shows that hypotheses H₁, H₂, H₃, H₄, and H₅ were accepted because the increase of these factors will lead to an increase in the influence of choice on the study abroad destination of Vietnamese students. From the results of the above analysis, it can be concluded that the theoretical model was consistent with the research data and the accepted research hypotheses.

4. Discussion and conclusions

This study examined the factors affecting the decision of Vietnamese students to choose to study in Russia. The main findings indicated that in general, the image of educational institutions in Russia and the promotional information were the factors that most influenced the choice of Vietnamese students to study in Russia. Meanwhile, the image of the Russian destination was the least influenced by the choice of Vietnamese students. Moreover, this paper shows novelty compared to previous studies by measuring the influence of all 5 factors on students' choice of study abroad destination on the dependent variable. A new factor that has been discovered and included in the research model was "destination image".

According to the research results, in order to attract international students to choose to study in Russia, we have proposed some recommendations as follows:

- 1) The image of higher education institutions and destination image needs to continue to be improved and enhanced in Russia;
- 2) it is necessary to build the image of Russia as an educational tourism destination;
- 3) information about higher education in Russia should be invested and developed to make it more known to international students through promotional programs;
- 4) the Russian government should have strict regulations on tuition fees at higher education

institutions as well as other living costs;
5) increase safety and security in Russian educational institutions and destinations in general.

This study has a theoretical model that is quite consistent with previous studies, so it can serve as a basis for further research and application to other study abroad destinations.

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